

Temple R

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Entry tags: Temple, Religious Group, Greek Cult, Greek Religions, Religious Place

Temple R is one of the earliest Greek stone temples in the Western Mediterranean, located in the southern sector of Selinunte's main urban sanctuary on the acropolis of the city. The building is nonperipteral, has an oikos plan (5.31 × 17.83m), and it consists, in its present state, of three rooms: a deep naos with two pilasters (not part of the original structure) along the main axis, a relatively deep adyton, and a rear room entered from the south and without communication with the other two chambers. Fronting the building and attached to its main front is a rectangular platform delimited by large ashlar blocks. Temple R was built around 570 BCE, heavily restored around 500 BCE after a fire, damaged and set on fire again during the Carthaginian sack of the city in 409 BCE, restored a second time, and plausibly lost its function as a temple around the middle of the 4th century BCE. Lastly, around 300 BCE this building and the surrounding ones were submerged by a thick fill that served as the base for a massive renovation of the whole area.

Date Range: 570 BCE - 300 BCE

Region: Temple R, Selinunte

Region tags: Italy, Sicily, Selinunte

Temple R on the acropolis of Selinunte, Sicily

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Marconi, C., and Ward, A. F. (2022). Temple R in Selinunte and the construction of tradition. *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1: 9-36.
- Source 2: Marconi, C. (2018a). La Dea del Tempio R, in *Gli Esametri Getty e Selinunte: Testo e Contesto*, edited by C. Antonetti, 179-202.
- Source 3: Cavallari, F.S. (1876). Selinunte. *Notizie degli Scavi di Antichità* 15: 45-46, 59, 106-109.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.visitselinunte.com/parco-archeologico/#templi>
- Source 1 Description: Official website with general information about the archaeological park, the history of the city and its monuments, and the nearby archaeological sites (in Italian)

– Source 2 URL: <https://ifa.nyu.edu/academics/selinunte/selinunte.htm>

– Source 2 Description: Official website of the NYU IFA Selinunte excavation (updated to 2014)

– Source 3 URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Selinunte>

– Source 3 Description: Wikipedia entry

Notes: Maybe: digitized books?

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1876; 2011-in progress

Notes: 1876: Cavallari 2011-in progress: New York University/University of Milan

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: Temple R is situated on the acropolis of Selinous, built on the S side of a naturally-occurring hill.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

Notes: The whole area was remodeled and raised a few times throughout the use of the temple: once to build Temple R over the previous buildings; once after and extensive fire around 500 BCE; and once between the end of the 5th and beginning of the 4th century BCE.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9–35.
<https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "The Carthaginian Conquest and Destruction of Selinus in 409 B.C.: Diodorus and Archaeology". In *The Destruction of Cities in the Ancient Greek World*, 85–107. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "Un Incendio Nel Tempio R Di Selinunte in Età Tardo Arcaica,". In *Studi in Onore Di Stefano Vassallo*, 31–35. Palermo, 2020.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Terracing

Notes: The whole acropolis was extended to the N and E with a large retaining wall in terraces (about 11m high) after 560 BCE

Reference: Chiarenza, Nicola. "Water, Social Space and Architecture at Selinous: The Case of the Urban Sanctuary". In *The Power of Urban Water: Studies in Premodern Urbanism*, 51–68. Berlin, 2020.

Reference: Mertens, Dieter. *Città E Monumenti Dei Greci D'occidente: Dalla Colonizzazione Alla Crisi Di Fine V Secolo A.c..* Rome: "L'Erma" di Bretschneider, 2006.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The urban sanctuary was separated from non-religious spaces by a wall following the edge of the plateau.

Reference: Chiarenza, Nicola. "Water, Social Space and Architecture at Selinous: The Case of the Urban Sanctuary". In *The Power of Urban Water: Studies in Premodern Urbanism*, 51–68. Berlin, 2020.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "War and the Life of a Sacred Structure. Weapons from the Nyu-unimi Excavations in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Fight for Greek Sicily: Society, Politics, and Landscape*, 18–46. Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2020.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The acropolis is the urban sanctuary of the city of Selinunte.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "New Evidence for Early Greek Settlement on the Acropolis of Selinunte". In *Listening to the Stones: Essays on Architecture and Function in Ancient Greek Sanctuaries in Honour of Richard Alan Tomlinson*, 252–61. Gloucester, 2019.

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: The whole city was connected to wider transportation networks via land (roads) and sea (two harbours).

– No

Notes: After the Carthaginian conquest of 409 BCE, the acropolis was used for shops (and possibly dwelling houses).

Reference: Chiarenza, Nicola. "Selinunte Tra La Seconda Metà Del Iv E Il Iii Secolo A.c. Un Insiediamento Dell'eparchia Cartaginese Al Centro Del Mediterraneo". *Karthago* 31 (2019): 27–63.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "The Carthaginian Conquest and Destruction of Selinus in 409 B.C.: Diodorus and Archaeology". In *The Destruction of Cities in the Ancient Greek World*, 85–107. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Reference: Helas, Sophie. *Selinus II. Die Punische Stadt Auf Der Akropolis.* Rome: Reichert, 2011.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Temple R is itself on top of structures EBI and EBII, which may have been its predecessors in terms of function.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "War and the Life of a Sacred Structure. Weapons from the Nyu-unimi Excavations in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Fight for Greek Sicily: Society, Politics, and Landscape*, 18–46. Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2020.

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<https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "New Evidence for Early Greek Settlement on the Acropolis of Selinunte". In *Listening to the Stones: Essays on Architecture and Function in Ancient Greek Sanctuaries in Honour of Richard Alan Tomlinson*, 252–61. Gloucester, 2019.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: The building has a rectangular plan (5.31 × 17.83m) consisting of three rooms: a deep naos with two pilasters (not part of the original structure) along the main axis; a relatively deep adyton; and a rear room entered from the south and without communication with the other two chambers. Fronting the building and attached to its main front is a rectangular platform.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9–35.
<https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Each phase of the temple had some other structures associated with it (e.g. the platform, the altar) that were part of that specific construction stage.

Reference: Mertens, Dieter. *Città E Monumenti Dei Greci D'occidente: Dalla Colonizzazione Alla Crisi Di Fine V Secolo A.c..* Rome: "L'Erma" di Bretschneider, 2006.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "The New Investigations of the Institute of Fine Arts - NYU in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Akragas Dialogue: New Investigations on Sanctuaries in Sicily*, 353–70. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2020.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9–35.
<https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Temple R is part of the main urban sanctuary of the city, situated on the acropolis.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Sacrificial

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, Andrew Ward, and Roberto Micciché. "Contextualizing an Animal Sacrifice in the Foundations of Temple R: A Preliminary Report of the Institute of Fine Arts - NYU Excavations on the Acropolis of Selinunte (2013-2015 Campaigns)". *Mare Internum* 9 (2017): 71-88. <https://doi.org/10.19272/201731401005>.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9-35. <https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

– Worship

Reference: Bellia, Angela. "Afterword: Musical Instruments as Votive Gifts". In *Musical Instruments as Votive Gifts in the Ancient World*, 89-102. Pisa; Rome, 2018.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9-35. <https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

Worship:

– Communal

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, Valeria Tardo, and Caterina Trombi. "The Archaic Pottery from the Institute of Fine Arts Excavations in the Main Sanctuary on the Akropolis of Selinunte". In *Sanctuaries and the Power of Consumption: Networking and the Formation of Elites in the Archaic Mediterranean World, Proceedings of the International Conference in Innsbruck, 20-23 March 2012*, 325-38. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2015.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and David Scahill. "The "south Building" in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte: A Theatral Structure?". In *The Architecture of the Ancient Greek Theatre*, 279-92. Aarhus, 2015.

– Individual

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and David Scahill. "The "south Building" in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte: A Theatral Structure?". In *The Architecture of the Ancient Greek Theatre*, 279-92. Aarhus, 2015.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, Valeria Tardo, and Caterina Trombi. "The Archaic Pottery from the Institute of Fine Arts Excavations in the Main Sanctuary on the Akropolis of Selinunte". In *Sanctuaries and the Power of Consumption: Networking and the Formation of Elites in the Archaic Mediterranean World, Proceedings of the International Conference in Innsbruck, 20-23 March 2012*, 325-38. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2015.

Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

|

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: - The first phase (ca. 570 BCE) consisted of the main structure and a rectangular hollow altar on the SE of the temple. - The rear chamber was added around 550 BCE, before the construction of the neighbouring Temple C - During the 5th and 4th century BCE there were two successive episodes of destruction and rededication: a fire around 500 BCE, which required a new floor and roof, and general reparations following the sack of the city by the Carthaginians in 409 - which included the digging of a large looting pit into the center of the adyton. - Around 300 BCE, with the construction of Temple B, the area was raised and the structure filled in preparation for a now-lost Hellenistic floor. This is also when Temple R lost its religious function and was deconsecrated.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "War and the Life of a Sacred Structure. Weapons from the Nyu-unimi Excavations in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Fight for Greek Sicily: Society, Politics, and Landscape, 18-46*. Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2020.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9-35.
<https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: Temple R was damaged by the construction of the neighbouring Temple C around 540 BCE, burned at least once in antiquity, damaged by war and looted in 409 BCE, and then destroyed by a series of earthquakes throughout the centuries.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of war

–As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: - The first phase (ca. 570 BCE) consisted of the main structure and a rectangular hollow altar on the SE of the temple. - The rear chamber was added around 550 BCE, before the construction of the neighbouring Temple C - During the 5th and 4th century BCE there were two successive episodes of destruction and rededication: a fire around 500 BCE, which required a new floor and roof, and general reparations following the sack of the city by the Carthaginians in 409 - which included the digging of a large looting pit into the center of the adyton. - Around 300 BCE, with the construction of Temple B, the area was raised and the structure filled in preparation for a now-lost Hellenistic floor. This is also when Temple R lost its religious function and was deconsecrated.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9-35. <https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

Reference: Mertens, Dieter. *Selinus I. Die Stadt Und Ihre Mauern..* Rome: Von Zabern, 2003.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "War and the Life of a Sacred Structure. Weapons from the Nyu-unimi Excavations in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Fight for Greek Sicily: Society, Politics, and Landscape*, 18-46. Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2020.

In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The walls of the back room have been partially reconstructed in pre-modern or early modern times, but we have no idea if all the blocks are in the right place as of now (chances are, they are not).

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The dedicatee of Temple R was a female deity, but no inscriptions mentioning her name have been found.

Notes: Archaeological finds and inscriptions found elsewhere listing the cults of Selinunte seem to support the attribution of Temple R to the cult of Demeter and Kore.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "La Dea Del Tempio R". In *Gli Esametri Getty E Selinunte. Testo E Contesto.*, 179-202. Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orso, 2018.

Reference: Bejor, Giorgio. "Problemi Di Localizzazione Di Culti a Selinunte". *Annali Della Scuola Normale Superiore Di Pisa - Classe Di Lettere E Filosofia* 7, no. 2 (1977): 439–57.

Reference: Pace, Biagio. "Il Megaron E Il Tempio C Di Selinunte E Gli Edifici Antichi a Due Navate E a Colonne Dispari Sul Fronte". *Monumenti Antichi Dell'accademia Dei Lincei* 28 (1922): 237–52.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "The New Investigations of the Institute of Fine Arts - NYU in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Akragas Dialogue: New Investigations on Sanctuaries in Sicily*, 353–70. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2020.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, Andrew Ward, and Roberto Micciché. "Contextualizing an Animal Sacrifice in the Foundations of Temple R: A Preliminary Report of the Institute of Fine Arts - NYU Excavations on the Acropolis of Selinunte (2013–2015 Campaigns)". *Mare Internum* 9 (2017): 71–88. <https://doi.org/10.19272/201731401005>.

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given the lack of inscriptions and written sources, it is impossible to ascertain whether the temple was exclusively used for the worship of a single deity, or whether there may have been other cults.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: Plausibly commissioned, funded, and built by the city, but the composition of the bureaucratic apparatus of Selinunte (and its hierarchy) is not documented

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The crossed spearheads under EBII (the direct predecessor of Temple R discovered underneath the cella) may be a symbol of spear-won land claimed by the first Greek settlers, and the temple might have been the result or a sign of that. Consequently, being Temple R built on top of EBII, it is possible that a memory of the original meaning of the foundation of tis religious structure might have been preserved.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "War and the Life of a Sacred Structure. Weapons from the Nyu-unimi Excavations in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Fight for Greek Sicily: Society, Politics, and Landscape*, 18–46. Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2020.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9–35. <https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: Unclear why the temple was founded in the first place. If it is indeed a temple of Demeter (among other gods?) who was the main deity of the metropolis Megara Nisaia, it would have made sense to establish a cult for her in the newly-founded apoikia.

Reference: Pace, Biagio. "Il Megaron E Il Tempio C Di Selinunte E Gli Edifici Antichi a Due Navate E a Colonne Dispari Sul Fronte". *Monumenti Antichi Dell'accademia Dei Lincei* 28 (1922): 237–52.

Reference: Bejor, Giorgio. "Problemi Di Localizzazione Di Culti a Selinunte". *Annali Della Scuola Normale Superiore Di Pisa - Classe Di Lettere E Filosofia* 7, no. 2 (1977): 439–57.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "La Dea Del Tempio R". In *Gli Esametri Getty E Selinunte. Testo E Contesto*, 179–202. Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orso, 2018.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No texts or inscriptions have been found, but it is possible that they were taken away and rehoused somewhere else when the temple was deconsecrated.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: Temple R and the platform at its entrance on the E façade are part of the same overall structure. An altar may have also existed, but it has not yet been discovered.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "New Evidence for Early Greek Settlement on the Acropolis of Selinunte". In *Listening to the Stones: Essays on Architecture and Function in Ancient Greek Sanctuaries in Honour of Richard Alan Tomlinson*, 252–61. Gloucester, 2019.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9–35. <https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The platform at the entrance abuts the temple's façade.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: While not of colossal dimensions, Temple R is nonetheless a monumentalization of the earlier phase of the religious area (buildings EBI and EBII).

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9–35. <https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "New Evidence for Early Greek Settlement on the Acropolis of Selinunte". In *Listening to the Stones: Essays on Architecture and Function in Ancient Greek Sanctuaries in Honour of Richard Alan Tomlinson*, 252–61. Gloucester, 2019.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The blocks of the temple are made of local limestone.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: There would have been metal alloy elements, most plausibly bronze, throughout the building (e.g. nails, hinges, hooks, decorations.).

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and James R. McCredie. *Temple Decoration and Cultural Identity in the Archaic Greek World*. Cambridge University Press, 2007.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Temple_Decoration_and_Cultural_Identity.html?hl=&id=THqZQfOzOysC.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9–35.

<https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "Un Acroterio Equestre Da Selinunte?". In *Antico E Non Antico: Scritti Multidisciplinari Offerti a Giuseppe Pucci, 377-84*. Milan-Udine, 2018.

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The roof of the temple featured architectural terracottas and tiles with a colourful decoration, as well as (possibly) acroteria shaped like riders.

↳ On the inside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The acroteria of Temple R might have been equestrian sculptures.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "Un Acroterio Equestre Da Selinunte?". In *Antico E Non Antico: Scritti Multidisciplinari Offerti a Giuseppe Pucci, 377-84*. Milan-Udine, 2018.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The acroteria of Temple R might have been equestrian sculptures.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "Un Acroterio Equestre Da Selinunte?". In *Antico E Non*

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract
– Yes

↳ Floral motifs
– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
– Yes

Notes: Decoration outside the temples was visible to everyone. However, access to the sacred buildings would be restricted, so that the decoration inside the temple was hidden to almost everyone.

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:
– No

Notes: No statues have been discovered in the temple, but it must have housed at least one image of the titular deity.

– Yes

Notes: All statues have been looted or destroyed, but the temple must have likely had at least one cult image of the titular deity.

↳ Cult statues:
– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Statues of humans:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

Notes: No reliefs have been found in the temple, but this information may change with new discoveries.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No inscriptions have been discovered in Temple R.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The discovery of fragments of architectural terracottas has lead archaeologists to hypothesize the presence of an acroterion shaped like a mounted rider. This figure might have been a supernatural being.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "Un Acroterio Equestre Da Selinunte?". In *Antico E Non Antico: Scritti Multidisciplinari Offerti a Giuseppe Pucci, 377-84*. Milan-Udine, 2018.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humans

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human narratives

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: The answer to this question changes depending on how one interprets the question - a goddess is seemingly the supreme deity of the temple, but she is not the head of the Selinuntine pantheon.

– Yes

Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Terracotta images of what is most plausibly the titular deity of the temple show her in the shape of a woman with long hair wearing a polos.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "La Dea Del Tempio R". In *Gli Esametri Getty E Selinunte. Testo E Contesto*, 179–202. Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orso, 2018.

Are they sky deity:

– No

Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: The goddess seems to have had at the very least a chthonic aspect, as shown by the discovery of the remains of burned piglets collected underneath upside-down cups and other vessels.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "La Dea Del Tempio R". In *Gli Esametri Getty E Selinunte. Testo E*

Contesto, 179–202. Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orso, 2018.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, Andrew Ward, and Roberto Micciché. "Contextualizing an Animal Sacrifice in the Foundations of Temple R: A Preliminary Report of the Institute of Fine Arts - NYU Excavations on the Acropolis of Selinunte (2013–2015 Campaigns)". *Mare Internum* 9 (2017): 71–88. <https://doi.org/10.19272/201731401005>.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "The New Investigations of the Institute of Fine Arts - NYU in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Akragas Dialogue: New Investigations on Sanctuaries in Sicily*, 353–70. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2020.

– No

Notes: The chthonic aspect is not the only characteristic of the goddess, so categorizing her as exclusively chthonic would be reductive.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: The goddess of Temple R has several aspects, and chthonic is but one of them.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although people worshipped and performed rituals and sacrifices, we do not know whether the goddess 'answered' them.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: A cult statue was almost surely present, but it has not been discovered in situ nor identified in a museum collection. It is also possible that it was removed when Temple R was deconsecrated.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "The New Investigations of the Institute of Fine Arts - NYU in the Main Urban Sanctuary of Selinunte". In *The Akragas Dialogue: New Investigations on Sanctuaries in Sicily, 353-70*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2020.

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↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– No

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that the cult statue was hosted in the most secluded part of the temple, and as such was hidden from pilgrims and the general public.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: The evidence shows that visitors were communicating (or attempting to communicate) with the gods through offerings and animal sacrifices.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological evidence suggests that various kinds of rituals were performed in and around the temple: animal sacrifices (and perhaps meals following them), libations, and possibly dance and musical performances.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, and Andrew Ward. "Temple R in Selinunte and the Construction of Tradition". *Journal of Ancient Architecture* 1 (2022): 9–35. <https://doi.org/10.19272/202214301001>.

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↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifices and/or burning of large animals in situ.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Not possible to estimate.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: No sacred calendar from Selinous has survived, so it is not possible to answer this question. As the titular deity of this sanctuary was a goddess associated (among other things) with fertility and agriculture, it is plausible that there would be seasonal celebrations and sacrifices to propitiate good crops for the year. The city may have also celebrated other local festivities, as well as some of the same ones as its metropolis, Megara Hyblaia.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Drinking vessels have been discovered around the temple. It is plausible that ritual consumption of wine or other substances took place during religious celebrations.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: check Roberto's articles

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: SECONDARY DEPOSITIONS

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Specific material offerings seem to have been suspended from the ceiling or mounted on the walls (e.g. antlers, pinakes) at some point

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - field doesn't know
- ↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: (check where)

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: No religious calendar for Selinunte has survived. However, since Temple R is one of the earliest religious establishments in the city, it is plausible that it was also at the center of religious festivals (with sacrifices?).

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The variety in quality and origin of votive offerings seems to suggest that access to the sanctuary was not restricted to specific classes of citizens - or only to citizens at all.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Not possible to estimate.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Notes: No data indicates that food consumption was limited to certain members of the population.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: A community of religious specialists must have existed to run the place, but there is no archaeological data confirming or denying it.

↳ Present full time
– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is very plausible that a formal bureaucracy existed at the temple, but at this time there is no evidence for it.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Animal-based protein might have been cooked and served for part of the population after sacrifices and festivals.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente, Andrew Ward, and Roberto Micciché. "Contextualizing an Animal Sacrifice in the Foundations of Temple R: A Preliminary Report of the Institute of Fine Arts - NYU Excavations on the Acropolis of Selinunte (2013–2015 Campaigns)". *Mare Internum* 9 (2017): 71–88. <https://doi.org/10.19272/201731401005>.

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Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Field doesn't know

Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Function for water management:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Religious rituals (possibly for the female side of the community): music, dances, night processions, some sort of performances

Notes: The neighbouring South Building and the space in front of it were plausibly used as an open-air theatral space for performances of various nature. The discovery of musical instruments and pottery representing women dancing to the sound of music seem to suggest that some rituals involving dance could have happened in front of (and in connections with the cult of) Temple R.

Reference: Marconi, Clemente. "Two New Aulos Fragments from Selinunte: Cult, Music and Spectacle in the Main Urban Sanctuary of a Greek Colony in the West". In *Musica, Culti E Riti Nell'occidente Greco*, 105–16. Pisa; Rome: Fabrizio Serra, 2014.

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Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

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